

ORIGINAL IMAGE

The First His Bundle Pacing Experience in a Young Child in Kazakhstan

Ayan Abdrakhmanov, MD^{1*}; Nurkanat Madreymov, MD¹; Aygerim Zhanatkyzy, MD¹;
Tatyana Ivanova-Razumova, MD¹; Zhanasyl Suleymen, MD¹

Keywords: child; His bundle pacing; selective

Despite the remaining debate regarding the optimal pacing site, traditional right ventricular (RV) pacing has been used successfully for bradyarrhythmia management for decades. The harmful effects of long-term RV apical pacing (ventricular dyssynchrony) are well known. These effects caused interest in approaches that provided more physiological stimulation, specifically, His bundle pacing (HBP). His bundle pacing brings hope as an attractive model to achieve physiological pacing. We present a case of a 12-year-old boy with symptomatic sinus arrest who underwent successful permanent HBP implantation. He complained of episodes of syncope and was examined by a neurologist. Electroencephalography with an ECG tracer demonstrated sinus bradycardia with a heart rate as low as 45 beats per minute and then, a transition to sinus arrest lasting 7.5 seconds with a syncopal attack during the day (Figure 1 Panel A). In this regard, he was referred to a cardiologist. On physical examination, his height was 153 cm, his weight was 36 kg, and his body surface area was 1.26 m². On the ECG, sinus rhythm with an incomplete right-bundle

branch block pattern, and a QRS duration of 120 msec was seen (Figure 1 Panel B). On transthoracic echocardiography, the left ventricular ejection fraction was 60% without any structural abnormalities. We decided to implant a permanent pacemaker using HBP. The subfascial pocket was created by the blunt method. Two punctures through the axillary vein were performed. First, a 7F peel-away introducer was advanced through the guidewire, and a specialized delivery catheter instructed for HBP (SelectSite™ C315HIS, Medtronic) was advanced through the sheath and located around the superior aspect of the tricuspid annulus in the right anterior oblique projection. A 69-cm, 4.1F active fixation, lumenless electrode (SelectSecure™ MRI SureScan™ Model 3830) was introduced up to the tip of the sheath. With fine-tuning of the catheter using both clockwise and counterclockwise rotations, His bundle potential was searched on the pace-sense analyzer, and when the His potential was observed with small atrial and large ventricular potentials demonstrating distal His bundle location, a unipolar capture test was initiated. At the high output of 5V@1ms, a non-selective His capture was observed with a selective His capture threshold of 1.5V@1ms and loss of capture at 0.5V@1ms. The identical 12-lead surface ECG compared to the baseline ECG was obtained during capture tests (Figure 2 Panel A). Enough atrial slack was left, taking into account the growth of the child. Then, a standard atrial electrode was conventionally implanted in the right atrial appendage. A standard, dual-chamber pacemaker was connected to the electrodes and positioned in the pocket (Figure 2 Panel B). All electrical parameters and the left ventricular ejection fraction were stable, and no acute or late procedure-related complications were observed during the 16 months follow-up.

Correspondance*

Ayan Abdrakhmanov, MD, FHRS, FESC, FEHRA
ayan-3@mail.ru

¹Department of Interventional Arrhythmology,
National Research Cardiac Surgery Center, Astana,
Kazakhstan

Received: 28 February 2023

Accepted: 5 April 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025206

Table. Pacemaker, echocardiography, and laboratory parameters at baseline and 16 months follow-up.

Parameter	Baseline	Follow-up
RA electrode		
Sensitivity, mV	2.8	1.5
Capture threshold, V	1.0	1.0
Pulse width, msec	0.4	0.4
Impedance, Ω	588	680
RV electrode		
Sensitivity, mV	5.2	12.3
Capture threshold, V	1.0	1.0
Pulse width, msec	0.4	0.4
Impedance, Ω	744	750
LVEF, %	60	60
NT-ProBNP, pg/ml Reference range (0-125)	43.1	25.6

LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; NT-ProBNP, N-Terminal Pro-Brain Natriuretic Peptide; RA, right atrial; RV, right ventricular

No syncopal episodes were also detected during the follow-up. A summary of the device and echocardiography parameters with laboratory markers was presented in the table. Our case shows that HBP is implementable even in young children with syncope due to sinus arrest. With the help of HBP, we have physiological stimulation and stable electrical parameters at >12 months. In addition, a stable left ventricular function without dyssynchrony criteria was realized on echocardiography.

Conflict of Interests

None

Funding

The authors state that the current study received no financial support.

Figure 1. Electroencephalography tracings with electrocardiography tracing at the bottom showing marked sinus bradycardia with almost normal brain activity (a) and resultant sinus arrest with abnormal brain activity during arrest (b) (A). Preprocedural electrocardiography showing sinus rhythm with incomplete right bundle branch block (B).

Figure 2. Postprocedural electrocardiography showing atrial sensed ventricular paced rhythm with non-selective His bundle capture and identical 12-lead electrocardiography compared to baseline (A). The posteroanterior chest x-ray showing the optimal position and adequate slack of both leads (B).